

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

Hairudin¹, Ahmad Suriansyah², Muhammad Saleh³

^{1,2,3}Master of Education Administration Program, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin 70123, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe the strategy of school principals in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education. This research is qualitative descriptive research with multiple case studies. This research was conducted at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi . The key informants were the principal, vice principal and teachers who were determined by purposive sampling. Data collection techniques through interviews, observation and documentation. Data validity was carried out by data triangulation by means of source triangulation, technical triangulation and time triangulation. Data analysis using data analysis techniques Miles and Huberman which consists of data collection, data condensation, data presentation and conclusion, description or verification. The results of the study found that the strategy used by the principal in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education is through a communication strategy, coaching strategy, and partnership strategy

KEYWORDS: strategy, pedagogic competence, professional competence

INTRODUCTION

The challenges of the industrial revolution 4.0 must be responded quickly and precisely by school principals in the school environment so that they are able to increase school competitiveness in the midst of global competition. Strategic policies need to be formulated in various aspects starting from institutions, fields of study, curricula, resources, and innovation development (Taufikurrahman, 2021). Education is a conscious effort that is deliberately designed to achieve a predetermined goal. Education aims to improve the quality of human resources. One of the efforts to improve the quality of human resources is through the learning process in schools. In an effort to improve the quality of educational resources, teachers are a component of human resources that must be fostered and developed continuously.

In carrying out their functions as professional teachers, there are several things that hinder teachers including; Schools as one of the cultural centers are tasked with selecting the influence of factors that affect students. Real work, in the form of ideas, ideas, behavior patterns, habits produced by schools in order to achieve educational goals. The importance of teacher awareness to achieve educational goals is needed in order to develop the creative potential of students and all other efforts to develop school culture.

Educational transformation in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 requires teachers to innovate in implementing learning that generates creativity, skills, critical thinking, collaboration and communication. However, there are still many teachers who do not understand about pedagogic and professional competencies and their indicators so they are still unable to apply learning in a direction that raises creativity, critical thinking skills, collaboration and communication. Many teachers spend hours lecturing in front of students but do not give any knowledge to students. Lectures are still considered by some teachers as an effective method. Indeed, by delivering material in a lecture in front of students, the teacher can freely talk at length. But on the other hand, this method also carries the risk of student boredom to continue listening which leads to a decrease in student interest in learning (Hartono, 2014).

Learning is the essence of improving the quality of education in schools. And the principal plays a very important role in moving various components in the school so that the teaching and learning process at the school goes well (Suhardiman, 2012). Principals must understand learning, starting from planning, implementing, evaluating to follow-up plans as teacher coaching materials in improving their competence. The principal is a key figure for the success of a school. Therefore, school principals must have an effective and efficient strategy in developing pedagogical and professional competencies and their indicators.

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

Teachers must understand pedagogical competence and its indicators starting from (1) Mastering the characteristics of students from the physical, moral, spiritual, social, cultural, emotional, and intellectual aspects. (2) Mastering the theory and principles of educational learning. (3) Develop a curriculum related to the subjects taught. (4) Organizing educational learning. (5) Utilizing ICT for the benefit of learning. (6) Facilitating the development of students' potential to actualize their various potentials. (7) Communicating effectively, empathetically, and politely with students. (8) Carrying out assessment and evaluation of learning processes and outcomes. (9) Utilizing the results of assessment and evaluation for the benefit of learning. (10) Doing reflective action to improve the quality of learning.

Then the teacher must also understand professional competence and its indicators starting from (1) Mastering the material, structure, concepts and scientific mindset that supports the subjects being taught. (2) Mastering the competency standards and basic competencies of the subjects taught. (3) Develop learning materials taught creatively. (4) Develop professionalism in a sustainable manner by taking reflective action. (5) Utilizing information and communication technology to develop oneself. The research result stated that professional competency is important for the teacher (Dina Rika Yandini, Ahmad Suriansyah, 2022; Rudiansyah, Wahyu, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a multi-case study type at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi. The research instrument is the researcher himself. Data collection techniques used are in-depth interviews, observation and documentation. Respondents as Key Informants were principal and vice principal and teachers who were determined by purposive sampling. Data validity was carried out by data triangulation by means of source triangulation, technical triangulation and time triangulation. Data analysis using data analysis techniques Miles and Huberman which consists of data collection, data condensation, data presentation and conclusion, description or verification. Key informants are school principals, vice principals and teachers determined by purposive sampling. This research contains the school principal's strategy in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education through communication strategies, coaching strategies and partnership strategies .

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of in-depth interviews, observation and documentation while at school, the following research findings were obtained:

Focus 1

Communication Strategy of the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong in the Development of Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competence to improve the Quality of Education through presentations. While the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi held a special meeting and small discussion.

Focus 2

Principal Development Strategy of SMAN 1 Lampihong in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competence to improve the Quality of Education through making learning tools and teaching supervision. While the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi through In House Training and Micro Teaching.

Focus 3

The partnership strategy for the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong School in the Development of Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency is to improve the quality of education through forming a Team of Teacher Performance Assessment Assessors (PKG), Collaborating with school supervisors and Collaborating with the Center for Educational Information Technology and Communication (BTIKP) of South Kalimantan Province. Meanwhile, the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi through encouraging teachers to be actively involved in activities carried out by the Subject Teacher Consultation and Collaboration with school supervisors.

Based on the findings above, it can be described the flow of the Principal's Strategy in developing teacher Pedagogic and professional competencies in order to improve the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi.

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

Picture 1: The School Principal's Strategy Flow in developing teacher Pedagogic and professional competencies in order to improve the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi.

Discussion of the findings at Site 1 and Site 2 regarding the principal's strategy in developing teacher pedagogical and professional competencies in improving the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi is seen in the following description :

A. Principal Communication Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve the Quality of Education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi.

Building communication is the first step taken by the principals of SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi in developing teacher pedagogical and professional competencies. Through good, precise and effective communication, it will produce a comprehensive teacher understanding of the development of pedagogical and professional competencies and their indicators.

The results of the study revealed that choosing the right form of communication strategy, namely SMAN 1 Lampihong through (percentages) and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi through (special meetings and small discussions) which discussed indicators of pedagogic competence and professional competence became supporters of success in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competence. in order to improve the quality of education.

Knowing and understanding are the main assets that must be possessed by teachers in developing pedagogical competencies and their indicators starting from (1) Mastering the characteristics of students from the physical, moral, spiritual, social, cultural,

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

emotional, and intellectual aspects. (2) Mastering the theory and principles of educational learning. (3) Develop a curriculum related to the subjects taught. (4) Organizing educational learning. (5) Utilizing ICT for the benefit of learning. (6) Facilitating the development of students' potential to actualize their various potentials. (7) Communicating effectively, empathetically, and politely with students. (8) Carrying out assessment and evaluation of learning processes and outcomes. (9) Utilizing the results of assessment and evaluation for the benefit of learning. (10) Doing reflective action to improve the quality of learning.

Then the teacher must also understand professional competence and its indicators starting from (1) Mastering the material, structures, concepts and scientific mindsets that support the subjects being taught. (2) Mastering the competency standards and basic competencies of the subjects taught. (3) Develop learning materials taught creatively. (4) Develop professionalism in a sustainable manner by taking reflective action. (5) Utilizing information and communication technology to develop oneself.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion Imron et al., (2019) which states that the teacher competency development planning strategy is actually an inseparable part of the higher education development program in general. The success of the program will affect the quality of the tertiary institution itself. These programs need to be carried out regularly and continuously in order to actually create quality teachers and be able to drive the progress of higher education. On this basis, the development of teacher professionalism is a very important effort in the context of improving the quality of higher education.

The professionalism of teachers can be seen from the attitude or treatment of their colleagues. As stipulated in the teacher's code of ethics which states that teachers maintain professional relationships, family spirit, and social discord. This means that teachers are required to maintain relationships with fellow teachers in their work environment, as well as outside their work environment. If the teacher maintains communication and interaction with colleagues, it means that the teacher is acting in accordance with the teacher's code of ethics and this can be categorized as disciplinary action. Teacher professionalism can be seen from the teacher's attitude towards students. Dedicated teachers guide students to form complete Indonesian people who have a Pancasila spirit. In addition, it is also the principle of the teacher who must guide students, not only teaching and learning, educating and guiding students by paying attention to the character of each student (Martini et al., 2022; Suriansyah et al., 2022). The strategy of principal of a teaching institution in increasing the professional competence of teachers can be successful if academic supervision is carried out, teacher coaching, and teacher participation in teacher development programs. The strategy for increasing the professional competence of teachers will be successful if it is supported by the involvement of all members of the teaching institution, starting from principal of the teaching institution, teachers, administrative personnel of the teaching institution. The implementation of strategies for increasing teacher professional competence will be effective if they are carried out in frequent intensities and implemented in locations closest to teaching institutions. Novita et al., (2022) states that teacher professionalism is an important aspect because it determines the quality of the teaching and learning process. But in fact, there are still many teachers who are considered to have professionalism that has not met expectations. From an input-process-output perspective, factors that influence professionalism include transformational leadership, the climate of teaching institutions, work motivation, and teacher professionalism.

According to the Education and Culture Human Resource Development Agency for Education Quality Assurance "the general objective of continuous professional development is to improve the quality of educational services in teaching institutions or madrasahs in order to improve the quality of education" (Kemendikbud, 2012). This goal is in line with the goal of sustainable professional development put forward (Suhaimi, 2021), namely, on the one hand to improve student learning performance, and on the other hand to improve the quality of teaching institution services as a whole. So that in general the purpose of holding continuous professional development activities is to improve the quality of educational services in teaching institutions.

B. Principal Development Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competence to Improve the Quality of Education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi.

The results showed that the selection of the form of coaching strategy was carried out by the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong through (making learning tools and class supervision). While the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi through (In House Training and Micro Teaching) in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education.

The principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong through making learning tools conducts coaching which consists of making an annual program, making a semester program, studying the syllabus, making lesson plans, determining KKM, preparing teaching materials, keeping a teaching journal. The supervision activities in the class, the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong saw firsthand the development of teachers in applying their understanding of pedagogic and professional competencies. From the Lesson plan (RPP) made by the teacher then practiced directly during the teaching and learning process will reflect the extent of their understanding in applying the indicators that exist in pedagogic competencies such as (1) Mastering the characteristics of students from physical, moral, spiritual, social, cultural, emotional, and intellectual. (2) Mastering the theory and principles of educational learning. (3) Develop a curriculum related to the subjects taught. (4) Organizing educational learning. (5) Utilizing ICT for the benefit of learning. (6) Facilitating the development of students' potential to actualize their various potentials. (7) Communicating effectively, empathetically, and politely with students. (8) Carrying out assessment and evaluation of learning processes and outcomes. (9)

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

Utilizing the results of assessment and evaluation for the benefit of learning. (10) Doing reflective action to improve the quality of learning.

Even so, the indicators for professional competence start from (1) Mastery of material, structure, concepts and scientific mindsets that support the subjects being taught. (2) Mastering the competency standards and basic competencies of the subjects taught. (3) Develop learning materials taught creatively. (4) Develop professionalism in a sustainable manner by taking reflective action. (5) Utilizing information and communication technology to develop oneself.

The Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi conducts coaching through In House Training and Micro Teaching activities. In House Training activities are held once in a semester. The indicators on teacher pedagogic and professional competence that are considered lacking are those that are developed. Making Audio Video Based Learning Media is a topic in the activities carried out in In House Training activities. The In House Training activities carried out in schools were attended by all teacher boards. The purpose of this In House Training is to follow up on the results of special meeting activities and small discussions. Micro Teaching is the next step in the coaching strategy carried out by the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi in developing teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competence. When the teacher carries out Micro Teaching activities, it will be seen which indicators of the teacher's pedagogical and professional competencies have been well achieved. The Principal and Vice principal of Curriculum see directly when the teacher carries out Micro Teaching activities in the classroom.

Hairiyati et al., (2022) states the efforts made by managers of teaching institutions in this case the leader of teaching institutions in improving teacher performance, teacher job satisfaction in teaching institutions is largely determined by the managerial activities of leader of teaching institutions in motivating, encouraging them to be involved in all work in teaching institutions, encouraging the creation of good behavior good organizational culture, building shared commitments that will further improve the performance and job satisfaction of the education staff, both teachers and other education staff. Akbar et al., (2022) To achieve good learning outcomes, it is necessary to have the ability of principal of a teaching institution to supervise academically both in planning, implementing, monitoring and following up so that all activities that take place can be measured and directed according to the expected goals. The results of this study are in line with research Hidayah et al., (2022) which states that routine supervision activities are carried out by leader of teaching institutions for teachers as one of the activities that is seen as positive in improving the quality of the learning process and efforts to improve teacher teaching performance. Wiewanthy et al., (2022) states that academic monitoring is a method of assisting teachers in increasing the professionalism of the educational process. This success will increase if the academic supervision skills of the leader of teaching institutions are used not only to evaluate teacher performance in controlling the teaching and learning process, but also to assist teachers in improving their performance. (Wahyu & Saleh, 2022) revealed that the participation of teachers in training, be it In House Training as well as external training can improve the professional abilities of teachers.

This finding is in line with previous research (Saleh et al., 2021) which stated that training is able to develop teachers' professional abilities. The role of principal of a teaching institution as a supervisor is expected to increase teacher professionalism, which will have an impact on the performance of teaching institutions. Thus, principal of a teaching institution has a strategic role in increasing teacher professionalism (Bahriadi et al., 2022).

The results of this study are in line with research Norbaiti et al (2022) which states that the development of teacher professionalism has been carried out adequately. The development of teacher professionalism is carried out through upgrading activities, training; teacher working groups; and class supervision. 2) The leadership of the teachers has a decisive role in efforts to improve the quality of the teaching abilities of teachers. The role of principal of a teaching institution in developing the abilities of teachers is that of a facilitator, motivator, and supervisor. In this context, principal of a teaching institution takes the following efforts: (a) involves teachers in every upgrading and training opportunity, (b) encourages teachers to continue their education, (c) requires teachers to attend KKG activities and (d) assisting teachers who experience difficulties in managing the teaching and learning process.

C. Partnership Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve the Quality of Education at SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi.

The results of the study show that the choice of partnership strategy forms which was carried out by the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong through the formation of a Teacher Performance Assessment Assessor Team (PKG), collaboration with school supervisors and collaboration with the Educational Information Technology and Communication Center (BTIKP) of South Kalimantan Province. Meanwhile, the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi encouraged teachers to be actively involved in the Subject Teacher Consultation (MGMP) activities and cooperate with school supervisors in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education.

partnership strategy used by school principals in conveying the Pedagogical and professional competency development of teachers takes different forms, but the substance desired by the Principal is the same, namely the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

and the Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi encourages and provides opportunities for Teachers to work together with others other teachers in developing the Pedagogic and Professional Competence of teachers to improve the quality of education.

The Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong School through the partnership strategy he chose to form the Teacher Performance Assessment Assessor Team (PKG) hopes that when the assessor guides the teacher in making a Lesson plan (RPP) the matters discussed are starting from Core Competencies, Basic Competencies and Competency Achievement Indicators, learning objectives, learning materials, Learning Methods, learning media, learning resources and then continuing to monitor the teacher in the classroom when teaching and then providing input after the teaching process is complete. Through the instrument check list per indicator of pedagogic and professional competency, the assessor conveys which indicators have been touched by the teacher during the teaching and learning process in class.

Through collaboration with school supervisors, it is hoped that there will be interaction between school supervisors and teachers so that a discussion space emerges which is expected to trigger critical thinking processes, generate creativity, create collaboration and lead to communication. So that the end result is the development of teacher pedagogic and professional competencies will develop optimally. Then through collaboration with the Educational Information Technology and Communication Center (BTIKP) of South Kalimantan Province. Principals through the partnership program hold Bimtek in order to improve, develop and utilize the role of digital in learning media in schools. Such as Bimtek activities for making learning video animations and making learning videos in order to develop teacher pedagogic and professional competence.

Whereas the Principal of SMAN 1 Lampihong through the partnership strategy carried out by the Principal is to encourage teachers to actively participate in participating in the Subject Teacher Consultation (MGMP) activities. Because in this activity, all teachers who teach the same subjects gather, have the same frequency, different problems, different experiences. So it is hoped that joint collaboration will occur in developing teacher Pedagogic and Professional competencies. Through the collaboration of Subject Teacher Deliberation Activities (MGMP) the Principal gave a message to all teachers participating in the activity so that the existing indicators on pedagogic and professional competencies and their indicators became the main concern that would be discussed in the Subject Teacher Deliberation (MGMP) activities the. The Principal of SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi hopes that the presence of school supervisors at the school providing guidance to teachers will greatly benefit the development of teachers' Pedagogic and Professional Competence. With the guidance of the School Superintendent, things that are still not understood by the teacher can be discussed and given solutions by the School Supervisor so that the teacher's Pedagogic and Professional Competence can develop properly.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion of K arwati & Priansa (2016) which states that the role of principal of a teaching institution as a supervisor in creating teacher professionalism is to create a conducive institutional climate, namely by providing opportunities and opportunities for optimizing teacher potential. In this case, principal of a teaching institution must involve teachers, without discrimination, to be involved in activities that will support teacher professionalism. Principal of a teaching institution provides opportunities and opportunities for teachers to be creative and innovate so that these teachers can actualize themselves. This can create a creative culture in the teaching institution environment, which has an impact on the maturity of teachers in carrying out their duties in a professional manner. Agustina et al., (2021) states that the professionalism of educators is closely related to the quality of education, because the learning process as the core of education will depend on professional educators.

A supervisor must be able to optimize the leadership role that is spread within the hierarchical organization of teaching institutions. The role of leadership greatly influences the professional maturity of teachers, where principal of a teaching institution as a conductor, motivator and coordinator, needs to have a clear leadership role. Principal of a teaching institution is in charge of leading teachers to foster harmonious cooperation between teachers so as to generate enthusiasm and work motivation (Sabri et al., 2022). The results of this study are in line with (Hidayah et al., 2022; Puspitasari & Saleh, 2022; Wiewanthietal., 2022) what states that academic supervision is a form of partnership with school supervision which has an impact on developing teacher competence which will ultimately lead to optimizing teacher performance.

CONCLUSION

The results showed that The principal's communication strategy in developing teacher pedagogical and professional competencies to improve the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong is through presentations. While at SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi through special meetings and small discussions discussing teacher pedagogic and professional competence. The strategy for fostering school principals in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong is through the manufacture of learning tools and through classroom supervision. While at SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi, the Principal conducts coaching for teachers through In House Training and Micro Teaching activities. The principal's partnership strategy in developing teacher pedagogic and professional competencies to improve the quality of education at SMAN 1 Lampihong is the formation of a Team of Teacher Performance Assessment Assessors (PKG), collaboration with school supervisors and collaboration with the Education Information and Communication Technology Center (BTIKP) Kalimantan Province South. While at SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi, this is to encourage teachers to be active in participating in Subject Teacher Consultation (MGMP) activities and partnerships with school supervisors.

Principal's Strategy in Developing Teacher Pedagogic and Professional Competency to Improve Education Quality (Multi-Case Study At SMAN 1 Lampihong and SMAN 1 Tebing Tinggi)

REFERENCES

- 1) Agustina, F., Suriasyah, A., & Asniwati. (2021). Teacher Professionalism Development. *Journal of K6 Education and Management* , 4 (2), 207–216. <https://doi.org/10.11594/jk6em.04.02.09>
- 2) Akbar, MN, Saleh, M., &Mahrita. (2022). Correlation Between Principal Academic Supervision, Self-Concept, Work Ethos Toward Teacher Performance of Junior High School Teachers in Hulu Sungai Selatan Regency. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research* , 05 (06), 2354–2363. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-60>
- 3) Bahriadi, Suriasyah, A., &Sulaiman. (2022). Continuous Professional Development Model to Improve Teacher Professional Competence. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research* , 05 (12). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i12-89>
- 4) Dina Rika Yandini, Ahmad Suriasyah, A. (2022). International Journal of Social Science And Human Research The Effect of Transformational Leadership of School Principles , Quality Culture and Job Satisfaction on Teacher Performance. 05(06), 2345–2353. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i12-28>
- 5) Hairiyati, Sulaiman, &Novitawati. (2022). The Influence of Principal Managerial Activities and Organizational Culture on Performance through Job Satisfaction of Elementary School Teachers in South Paringin District. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-104>
- 6) Hartono, R. (2014). *Variety of Teaching Models that are Easy for Students to Accept* . DIVAPress.
- 7) Hidayah, N., Saleh, M., & Suhaimi. (2022). The Effect of Principal Academic Supervision, Teacher Self-Efficacy and Teacher Discipline on Teacher Performance at SDN Martapura District, Banjar Regency. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-108>
- 8) Imron, A., Dewi, VA, Sonhadji, A., & Suriasyah, A. (2019). Lecturer Development Competency Management in Improving the Quality of Education and Teaching. *The 4th International Conference on Education and Management (COEMA 2019)* , 94–99.
- 9) Martini, Ahmad, KI, & Metroyadi. (2022). The Correlation among Teacher Professionalism, Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Teacher Performance. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06), 2230–2235. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-30>
- 10) Mulyasa, E. (2019). *School Based Management, Strategic and Implementation Concepts* . BumiKasara.
- 11) Norbaiti, S., Suriasyah, A., &Sulaiman. (2022). Effect of Principal Transformational Leadership Professional Development and Competence on the Professionalism of State Junior High School Teachers in Balangan Regency. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-99>
- 12) Novita, W., Sulaiman, & Rizalie, M. (2022). Work Motivation as an Intermediary Variable in the Relationship between Principal Transformational Leadership, School Climate, and Teacher Professionalism. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-51>
- 13) Rudiansyah, Wahyu, S. (2022). The Role of Work Culture in Mediating the Effect of Professional Competence and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 05(06), 2321–2327. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-42>
- 14) Sabri, M., Saleh, M., &Sulaiman. (2022). The Contribution of Principal Supervision and Motivation of Teacher Work Towards Teacher Attitudes to Work and Implementation of Teaching at State Junior High School in Bati-Bati District, Tanah Laut Regency. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research* , 05 (06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-100>
- 15) Saleh, M., Suriasyah, A., & Anita. (2021). The Influence of Motivation, Guidance and Counseling Teacher Activities in Deliberation and Professionalism. *Journal of K6 Education and Management* , 4 (2), 129–135. <https://doi.org/10.11594/jk6em.04.02.02>
- 16) Suriasyah, A., Halimah, & Sulistiyana. (2022). The Effect of Professional Competency and Communication on Work Productivity through Teacher Work Discipline. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research* , 4355–4360. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i9-49>
- 17) Wahyu, & Saleh. (2022). Teacher Academic Supervision toward Learning Quality through Competence and Work Motivation of Teachers in A-Accredited Public Senior High Schools in Barito Kuala. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research* , 4678–4381. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i9-52>
- 18) Wieyanthi, N., Wahyu, &Sulaiman. (2022). The Relationship between Principal Managerial Activities and Academic Supervision Activities through Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance at SDN MurungPudak District. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research* , 05 (06), 2306–2312. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v5-i6-40>